

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELECTED FITNESS VARIABLES AND CYCLING ROAD RACE PERFORMANCE AMONG MALE ROAD CYCLIST

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Cite This Article: Nandakumar M & Rajinikumar Palaniyappan, "Relationship Between Selected Fitness Variables and Cycling Road Race Performance Among Male Road Cyclist", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 96-101, 2023.

Abstract:

Purpose: The study aimed to examine the relationship between selected fitness variables speed, agility, cardiovascular endurance, muscular power, muscular endurance, and flexibility and 50 km road cycling performance among male cyclists.

Methodology: Thirty male cyclists aged 18-28 years with over five years of training experience were tested using standardized assessments, including a 30m sprint, T-test, standing broad jump, 12-minute run/walk, push-ups, and sit-and-reach. Cycling performance was measured over a 50 km course. Pearson's correlation was used to analyse relationships between fitness variables and performance.

Results: Speed and agility were positively correlated with cycling performance, while cardiovascular endurance, muscular endurance, and muscular power were negatively correlated. Flexibility showed no significant relationship.

Conclusion: For mid-distance road cycling, explosive speed and agility are key predictors of performance, whereas traditional endurance and power measures have less influence, emphasizing the need for targeted, event-specific training.

Key Words: Cycling Road Race, Fitness, Speed, Agility, Cardiovascular Endurance, Muscular Power, Muscular Endurance and Flexibility

1. Introduction:

Road cycling is a common type of cycling that is done on paved roads and places an emphasis on efficiency, speed, and endurance over longer distances. It is both a recreational pastime and a competitive sport with different race formats, and it uses lightweight bikes made for performance and aerodynamics. Road cycling is a complete fitness activity that improves muscular endurance and cardiovascular health (USA Cycling, 2025). Studies reveal a strong correlation between road riding and fitness metrics. Because it strengthens the heart muscles, increases lung capacity, and improves blood circulation, cycling continuously increases cardiovascular fitness and lowers the risk of cardiovascular disorders (Smith et al., 2021; Shah et al., 2021).

Road cycling improves muscle endurance, especially in the lower limbs, which is important for long-distance riding since it allows for prolonged pedalling efficiency. riding economy, aerobic metabolism, and anaerobic power are further enhanced by strength training in conjunction with endurance riding, which enhances total cycling fitness and performance (Vikmoen et al., 2021; Ried-Larsen et al., 2021). An efficient aerobic activity that is known to enhance cardiovascular fitness and autonomic function is road cycling. A 12-week progressive aerobic cycling training program showed notable gains in muscle strength, heart rate recovery (HRR), a crucial measure of autonomic regulation, and peak oxygen consumption (VO₂peak) in research including chronic stroke patients. Increased VO₂peak and HRR have been positively correlated, indicating that cycling improves cardiovascular autonomic regulation as well as aerobic capacity. This is important for exercise rehabilitation and cardiovascular health in general (Jin et al., 2013).

Cycling performance is greatly influenced by agility since it helps a rider react quickly to obstacles and keep control of their bike. Reaction time and bicycle-specific agility are related, according to research, with higher exercise intensities improving cognitive arousal and choice reaction time. This improved reaction time at high-intensity cycling emphasizes the value of agility training for cyclists by preventing collisions and maintaining bike control (Buchholtz, 2020). Road cycling speed is affected by a number of variables, including rider fitness, cadence, power output, and neuromuscular efficiency. Greater cycling speeds are possible with higher cadence and power, but neuromuscular fitness which entails quick muscle activation and coordination is necessary for peak performance. Research suggests that maintaining a chosen cadence while pedalling reduces neuromuscular fatigue and improves power production efficiency (Mater et al., 2021). The purpose of the study is to find the relationship between selected fitness variables (speed, agility, cardiovascular endurance, muscular power, muscular endurance and flexibility) and cycling road race performance.

2. Methodology:

2.1 Selection of Subjects:

The purpose of this study was to analyse the relationship between anthropometric variables and cycling

50-kilometer road race performance among male road race cyclists. To facilitate the study 30 male cyclists were randomly selected from various universities and clubs in Tamil Nadu in the age group from 18 to 28 years with the training experience of above 5 years.

Table 1: Demographic Data

Parameter	Mean	Range	SD
Age	21.3	18-28	2.1
Weight	70.2	58-85	7.8
Height	175.64	165-189	6.4
Training Years	6.5	4-10	2.3

2.2 Selection of Variables:

The selected variables for this research are:

Table 2: Selection of variables

S.No	Independent Variables	Dependent Variable
1	Speed (s)	Cycling Road Race Performance
2	Agility (s)	
3	Muscular Power (m)	
4	Cardiovascular Endurance (m)	
5	Muscular endurance (Counts)	
6	Flexibility (cm)	

2.3 Test Administration:

Table 3: Tools used for data collection

S.No	Variables	Tools
1	Speed	Stop watch
2	Muscular power	Measuring tape
3	Cardiovascular endurance	Stop watch and cones
4	Agility	Stop watch and cones
5	Muscular endurance	-
6	Flexibility	Sit and reach box
7	50km cycling performance	Timer

The subjects were done with warm ups and certain drills before participating in the test. The purpose of this study is to find the relationship between selected fitness variables and cycling road race performance, to collect the necessary data the following variables were measured: speed, agility, muscular power, cardiovascular endurance, muscular endurance, flexibility and 50km cycling performance.

To measure speed 30m sprint test was used in this procedure, the participant started from a standing start behind the designated starting line. On the starter's signal, the athlete sprinted forward as quickly as possible over a distance of 30 meters. Timing was started with the initiation of movement and ended when the subject's torso crossed the finish line. The test was administered on a flat, non-slippery surface, and three trials was performed, the best time was considered for analysis (Getchell, 1979).

Figure 1: 30m Sprint

The standing broad jump evaluates lower body muscular power by measuring the distance an individual can propel themselves forward from a stationary position. The participant stands with feet shoulder-width apart behind a marked take-off line. Using a countermovement of the knees and arms, the athlete jumps forward as far as possible, landing on both feet without falling backward. The distance is measured from the take-off line to the back of the heels at landing. Three attempts are usually given, and the longest jump is recorded as the score (Getchell, 1979).

Figure 2: Standing Broad Jump

The Cooper 12-minute run/walk test is designed to assess cardiovascular endurance by measuring the maximum distance an individual can cover within 12 minutes. Conducted on a measured track the participant is instructed to run or walk at the fastest sustainable pace for the duration of the test. At the conclusion of 12 minutes, the total distance travelled is recorded. This test provides an estimate of aerobic capacity and is frequently used in both athletic and general fitness settings (Getchell, 1979).

The T-Test was used to measure agility, which is the ability to rapidly change direction while maintaining speed and balance. Four cones were arranged in a “T” formation, with one at the base, one at the intersection, and two spaced laterally at the top. Beginning at the base cone, the participant sprints forward to touch the middle cone, then shuffles laterally to touch the cone on one side, moves across to touch the opposite side cone, shuffles back to the center, and finally backpedals to the starting point. Timing started on the initial movement and stopped when the participant returned to the base cone (Getchell, 1979).

Figure 3: T-Test Set up (Raya et al., 2013)

The push-up test is a measure of upper body muscular endurance. The participant began in the standard push-up position with hands placed shoulder-width apart and the body held in a straight line from head to heels. A full push-up consists of lowering the body until the elbows are bent at approximately 90 degrees or until the chest nearly touches the ground, followed by extending the arms to return to the starting position. The test continued until the participant reaches muscular fatigue or fails to maintain proper form. The number of correctly executed repetitions is recorded as the score (Getchell, 1979).

Figure 4: Push-up Test

The sit-and-reach test is commonly used to assess flexibility of the lower back and hamstring muscles. The participant sat on the floor with legs extended straight ahead, feet placed flat against a sit-and-reach box and knees fully extended. With one hand placed over the other, the participant slowly reached forward along the measuring scale as far as possible without bouncing, holding the position momentarily. The farthest point reached is recorded in centimetres, and typically the best of three trials is taken as the score (Getchell, 1979).

Figure 5: Sit and Reach Test

50km Cycling Road Race Performance

The timing of the 50 km cycling road race was measured using a standardized procedure to ensure accuracy and reliability. The course distance was pre-measured using GPS mapping software. Each participant began from a standing start after completing a 10-minute standardized warm-up, and timing was initiated using a stopwatch. Finish times were recorded at the 50 km mark. All race times were recorded in minutes (International Cycling Union [UCI], 2021).

The data were normally distributed. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used to perform the statistical calculations. To find the correlation the Pearson's product moment correlation was used to test the significance level. The nature of data of all variables selected for this study was in ratio and the level of significance was set with 0.05 (5 percentage).

3. Results and Discussions:

The minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of selected biomechanical variables of male cyclists were presented in the table - 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of the selected variables

S.No	Variables	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD (\pm)
1	Cycling road race performance (minutes)	30	77.4	87	81.87	2.60
2	Speed test (30m sprint) - s		3.95	4.40	4.16	0.12
3	Agility (T test) - s		10.35	11.50	10.84	0.32
4	Flexibility (sit and reach) - cm		12	23	17.3	2.78
5	Cardiovascular endurance (12 minutes run and walk) - m		2600	3100	2855	127.59
6	Muscular endurance (Pushups) - counts for 1 minute		35	50	42	4.18
7	Muscular power (SBJ) m		2.40	2.70	2.55	0.08

Table 5: Inter-Correlation of selected Anthropometric variables and Cycling Road Race Performance

Variables	Cycling Road Race Performance	Speed	Agility	Flexibility	Cardiovascular Endurance	Muscular Endurance	Muscular Power
Cycling Road Race Performance	1	0.961**	0.956**	-0.306	-0.965**	-0.955**	-0.967**
Speed		1	0.992**	-0.358	-0.976**	-0.982**	-0.962**
Agility			1	-0.368*	-0.967**	0.950**	-0.961**
Flexibility				1	0.338	0.385*	0.250
Cardiovascular Endurance					1	0.963**	0.989**
Muscular Endurance						1	0.950**
Muscular Power							1

Table value with df 28 at 0.05 level of significance was 0.361.

*Significant at 0.05.

**Significant at 0.01

- It was evident from the table - 5 that the cycling road race performance was positively correlated with speed ($r = 0.961$, $p < 0.05$) and agility (0.956 , $p < 0.05$). The cycling road race performance was negatively correlated with cardiovascular endurance (-0.965 , $p < 0.05$), muscular endurance (-0.955 , $p < 0.05$) and muscular power (-0.967 , $p < 0.05$). The flexibility ($p > 0.05$) was not significantly correlated with cycling road race performance.
- It was evident from the table - 5 that the speed was positively correlated with agility (0.992 , $p < 0.05$). The speed was negatively correlated with cardiovascular endurance (-0.976 , $p < 0.05$), muscular endurance (-0.982 , $p < 0.05$) and muscular power (-0.962 , $p < 0.05$). The flexibility ($p > 0.05$) was not significantly correlated with speed.
- It was evident from the table - 5 that the agility was positively correlated with muscular endurance (0.950 , $p < 0.05$). The agility was negatively correlated with flexibility (-0.368 , $p < 0.05$), cardiovascular endurance (-0.967 , $p < 0.05$) and muscular power (-0.961 , $p < 0.05$).
- It was evident from the table - 5 that the flexibility was positively correlated with muscular endurance (0.385 , $p < 0.05$). The flexibility was not significantly correlated with cardiovascular endurance ($p > 0.05$) and muscular power ($p > 0.05$).
- It was evident from the table - 5 that the cardiovascular endurance was positively correlated with muscular endurance (0.963 , $p < 0.05$) and muscular power (0.989 , $p < 0.05$).
- It was evident from the table - 5 that the muscular endurance was positively correlated muscular power (0.950 , $p < 0.05$).

3.1 Discussions:

The present study aimed to examine the relationship between selected fitness variables (speed, agility, cardiovascular endurance, muscular power, muscular endurance, and flexibility) and 50 km cycling road race performance among male cyclists. The results revealed significant correlations, indicating that specific fitness components influence cycling performance differently.

The study found that speed (30m sprint) and agility (T-test) were positively correlated with cycling performance ($r = 0.961$ and $r = 0.956$, $p < 0.05$, respectively). This suggests that cyclists with faster sprinting ability and better agility can achieve improved performance in road races. These findings align with previous research indicating that explosive speed and rapid directional changes are crucial for race positioning, breakaways, and sprint finishes (Bompa & Haff, 2009; Chaouachi et al., 2014).

Cardiovascular endurance, muscular endurance, and muscular power showed negative correlations with cycling performance ($r = -0.965$, -0.955 , and -0.967 , $p < 0.05$, respectively). Endurance capacity and muscular power are generally important in cycling, these results may reflect the nature of the short-duration, high-intensity demands of the 50 km road race, where cyclists with relatively higher speed and agility can maintain better performance over the course compared to those optimized primarily for maximal endurance or power output. This is consistent with studies describing that cycling performance is influenced by the specific balance of anaerobic and aerobic capacities depending on the race format (Faria et al., 2005; Joyner & Coyle, 2008).

Flexibility, measured by the sit-and-reach test, was not significantly correlated with cycling performance ($r = -0.306$, $p > 0.05$). This indicates that flexibility may play a minor role in cycling efficiency for road races, as cycling performance depends more on the optimization of power production, biomechanics, and endurance rather than maximal range of motion (McNair et al., 2000).

The inter-correlations among the fitness variables revealed that speed and agility were positively related ($r = 0.992$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that athletes with faster sprinting capacity also exhibited superior agility. Similarly, strong positive correlations were observed among cardiovascular endurance, muscular endurance, and muscular power ($r > 0.95$), indicating that these variables often develop together in trained athletes and reflect an integrated physiological profile. However, their negative relationship with cycling performance in this study highlights the need to tailor training programs to the specific demands of the event (Bompa & Haff, 2009).

Overall, the findings emphasize that speed and agility are critical predictors of performance in a 50 km road cycling race, while traditional endurance and muscular power variables may not always correlate positively, depending on the specific race conditions. Coaches can use these insights to prioritize speed and agility-focused training for cyclists participating in mid-distance road races.

4. Conclusions:

The study revealed that speed and agility are positively associated with 50 km road cycling performance, making them key predictors of success in such races. In contrast, cardiovascular endurance, muscular endurance, and muscular power showed negative correlations, while flexibility had no significant effect. These findings suggest that for mid-distance road cycling, performance is more influenced by explosive speed and agility than by traditional endurance or power measures, highlighting the importance of targeted training for these specific fitness components.

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